

Democratizing Predictive Analytics with Generative Artificial Intelligence towards AI-Native Networks

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Abstract—In the rapidly advancing era of Artificial Intelligence (AI), the transformative force of foundation models has streamlined the automated generation of multi-modal content, corresponding to user intents. At the same time, Machine Learning (ML), particularly Deep Learning (DL), has achieved state-of-the-art performance in optimization and inference tasks of various domains, including telecommunications. However, the segregation of technological domains poses challenges to the integration of powerful AI/ML capabilities towards realizing the vision of “AI-native” networks, such as future 6G networks that will provide ubiquitous intelligence across their infrastructure and service planes and will seamlessly adapt and evolve to support new classes of applications. This paper introduces Auto-TimeGPT, a hands-free Automated ML (AutoML) solution, extending the profound impact of Generative AI (GenAI) for Time Series Analysis, to networks and communications. The contribution includes an out-of-the-box zero-shot approach for anomaly detection and Time Series Forecasting (TSF) which is particularly useful for the Edge-Cloud orchestration framework CODECO, comprehensive in and out-of-domain evaluation, and a limitations analysis. Evaluation results across diverse real-world datasets demonstrate competitive performance with cutting-edge approaches based on Large Language Models (LLMs) and DL models, generalization and optimization ability and effective anomaly detection. The proposed framework democratizes AI analytics in communication and networking domains.

Index Terms—Automated Machine Learning, Generative AI, Zero-shot Inference, Internet of Things, Network Automation, TS, 6G, AI-native.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of rapid technological advancement, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force, reshaping the fabric of our daily lives, encompassing professional, educational and entertainment activities. With the meteoric rise of *Transformer* architectures, the power of AI has become increasingly evident, revolutionizing the way we interact with information and communicate. Machine Learning (ML) plays a pivotal role in this context, particularly in the realms of analytics and predictive insights, where advanced Deep Learning (DL) models achieve state-of-the-art (SoTA) performance across a plethora of domains, such as communications [1] and applications, e.g., anomaly detection [2].

At the same time, it is becoming obvious that despite the wide success of ML-related research in networking systems, still many challenges for applications in the communications

and networking domain remain, in order to easily and efficiently leverage powerful AI/ML capabilities and solutions towards realizing the vision of “AI-native” networks. Representative challenges are the overgrowing ML and domain expertise required to successfully model and approach a particular problem in complex communications domains such as future 6G systems, since misconceptions and false assumptions undermine the effectiveness of the ML solution. Some additional challenges are the lack of ground truth data, interpretability and robustness of the ML models, and communication bottlenecks in distributed ML systems [3].

The demand for cutting-edge, reliable, and trustworthy ML tools that overcome the aforementioned challenges has become pivotal for next generation networks such as 6G, which are envisioned to be fully autonomic and natively intelligent, providing ubiquitous access of AI services to anyone. In this pursuit, the accessibility and democratization of ML capabilities have become paramount, paving the way for innovative solutions like Time Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (TimeGPT) [4] to extend its transformative impact to myriads of applications in the domain of networks and communications. TimeGPT allows for effortless access to high-quality AI analytics to make data-driven decisions, by unlocking the power of accurate predictions and confident navigation of uncertainty, while eliminating the need for a dedicated team of ML engineers.

Prior research proposes innovative approaches to time series (TS) forecasting and proactive anomaly detection within the dynamic landscape of communications and networks. AI-based infrastructure resource usage algorithms can help Edge-Cloud orchestration frameworks, such as the CODECO management framework [5], reduce network outages by predicting resources overload ahead of time and proactively rerouting applications and running pods among network nodes. At the same time, leveraging AI techniques, they can study and track their networks behavior to accurately identify potential anomaly patterns, thus enhancing the capabilities of their network monitoring and assurance tools, greatly improving their intrusion detection capabilities, optimizing network performance and fortifying communication systems against emerging threats [6]. The synthesis of data analytics and predictive insights with AI techniques underscores their indispensable role in shaping the future of communications and networks.

This paper proposes a novel Automated ML (AutoML) solution, which we dub “Auto-TimeGPT”, for real-time AI analytics and predictive insights, with an advanced system architecture, using a cutting-edge generative pre-trained transformer model. The goal of this work is to provide an AutoML system that uses democratization of AI and flexibility as the main guiding principles to facilitate accurate anomaly detection. Thus, the contribution of this work is three-fold:

- A hands-free AutoML approach for anomaly detection and TS forecasting;
- A comprehensive in- and out-of-domain evaluation across two real-world and two synthetic diverse datasets of zero-shot inference, focusing on accuracy, fine-tuning and anomaly detection;
- Limitations analysis of the proposed framework that utilizes TimeGPT, the first general global model for TS.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides the related work. Section III presents our approach and its workflow. Evaluation results are discussed in Section IV and current limitations in Section V. Concluding remarks and future work are presented in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Forecasting models have become a prominent area of research, driven by their success in recent famous competitions [7]. However, creating a high-quality ML system for a specific task highly relies on human expertise, hindering the applications of ML to more areas. A growing number of researchers focus on AutoML, which is becoming a promising approach to build zero-touch ML systems. In [8] the authors discuss the need for practical ML systems that can be used off the shelf by non-experts, and automatically choose an appropriate algorithm, a preprocessing procedure and hyperparameters. The authors propose an AutoML system based on the Python package scikit-learn. The system takes into account past performance on similar datasets and constructs ensembles from the models evaluated during the optimization phase.

The authors of [9] discuss how conventional approaches either manually design or use Neural Architecture Search (NAS) to find a specialized neural network and train it from scratch for each case, which is computationally prohibitive (causing emissions as much as 5 cars’ lifetime) and thus unscalable. Therefore, they propose to train a Once-For-All network that supports diverse architectural settings to reduce the cost, allowing for inference without additional training.

In [10] the authors discuss the exponential data generation increase in Internet of Things (IoT) systems caused by the adoption of sensors and smart devices, posing challenges in ML model selection, tuning, and retraining, requiring ML expertise. To address these challenges, AutoML is gaining traction, automating ML model selection, construction, tuning, and updating. In this paper AutoML methods are explored for optimal application of ML algorithms in IoT data analytics and

anomaly detection. The paper concludes with a classification of challenges and research directions in this evolving domain.

The authors of [11] present the challenges that the traditional ML techniques face in Industrial IoT (IIoT) and the strong need for AutoML techniques that streamline the process, reducing the necessity for manual intervention and computational resources, thereby positioning themselves as a potentially transformative innovation in the Industry 4.0 era. This paper introduces two distinct models; AutoML employing PyCaret, and Auto Deep Neural Network (AutoDNN) based on AutoKeras, both aimed at accurate anomaly detection for predictive maintenance. Automating the ML process can decrease time and cost for various applications in the IIoT domain.

In [12] the authors also present the advantages of AutoML, reducing the demand of ML engineers and allowing for wider adoption in a plethora of fields. The authors however highlight that the research over TSF, involving the application of AutoML, is in an immature state. This paper proposes an AutoML approach that aggregates TSF models, with a special focus on the optimization phase, which employs genetic algorithms for hyperparameter tuning. A comparison between the proposed AutoML approach and recent TSF is presented, showing that the AutoML model surpasses the benchmark.

Based on the above, this work proposes a system building on the joint of AutoML, TSF and TimeGPT to facilitate the need for a democratized, accurate, out-of-the-box ML solution for predictive insights and anomaly detection, suitable for zero-shot inference on any TS dataset.

III. AUTO-TIMEGPT

The Auto-TimeGPT system offers a seamless out-of-the-box AutoML pipeline, written in Python programming language, capable of handling generic TS data and providing high-quality AI analytics and predictive insights. The main idea is that the user, who can be a developer, is not required to have any ML expertise or domain knowledge of the data. Two popular and generic-enough problems are supported, in order to allow the use of the pipeline in a wide variety of applications, as a supporting or core component; namely anomaly detection and TS forecasting. Additionally, optional parameters are supported for each problem, specifically prediction interval and forecasting horizon, respectively. A notable advantage is that no training is required. Moreover, Auto-TimeGPT offers the capability of fine-tuning the pipeline to make more informed strategic decisions and adapt to any particular domain.

TSF is a specialized area of forecasting that deals with the prediction of future values based on historical time-ordered data. Anomaly detection can be solved with TSF that predicts a range of values for the next time step, let’s call it $t + 1$ (where $t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$), instead of a single numerical prediction. We then check if the ground truth value with timestamp $t + 1$ is within this predicted range; if not, it is marked as an anomaly.

The Auto-TimeGPT workflow, shown in Figure 1, incorporates and implements elements of AutoML paradigms [13]

about data preprocessing and accuracy evaluation. Initially, the dataset provided by the user is parsed. In the case of a streaming-based pipeline, enough data has to be gathered in order to proceed to the next stage, since the pipeline requires a certain amount of data to treat as historical data in order to provide predictions. The amount depends on the particular problem and any potential user parameters, but a typical number of data points would be less than 10% of the dataset. The data is then preprocessed (cleaning, scaling, etc.) and TS metadata are detected (e.g. frequency). Without training, a prediction is performed and its accuracy is evaluated. If the evaluation phase is successful, the model is now ready to be served to the user as an endpoint; otherwise the job that fine-tunes the model on the data provided by the user is triggered, and the prediction and evaluation stages are repeated.

A. Data Preparation

Auto-TimeGPT handles missing data by imputing values based on its built-in strategies. It automatically identifies missing values and applies appropriate data imputation techniques, such as forward/backward fill and padding. Data Scaling is also performed automatically, where the input features are scaled to a similar range, by using techniques like Min-Max scaling and Standard Scaling. Similarly, data transformation, namely data validation, one-hot encoding, potential data type conversions and enhanced feature engineering, i.e. crucial date-related features generation, are handled automatically too.

Certain TS metadata, such as frequency, can play an important role in understanding the structure of the data. The pipeline has a designated stage for generic TS frequency detection. The internal algorithm of this stage, shown in Algorithm 1, returns the seasonal period for seasonal data, and the average cycle length for cyclic data. First, it removes the linear trend from the input TS. The detrended data are then transformed into the frequency domain using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). The algorithm attempts to identify peaks in the resulting spectrum. If peaks are detected, it extracts the frequency corresponding to the highest peak, calculates its period and handles cases where the period is infinite by finding the next local maximum. In case no dominant frequency is present, the period is set to one.

In order to implement this algorithm in Python, the SciPy module was used for FFT, detrending TS data and identifying peaks. The complexity of the detrending and identifying peaks in TS data is linear, whereas the complexity of FFT is $O(n \log_2 n)$, dominating the overall time complexity of the algorithm. It is important to note that the logarithmic complexity of the algorithm can be avoided in cases where the required metadata can be inferred either from the data structure that represents the data, such as the popular DataFrame data structure provided in Python, or from the input parameters of the user, who may provide the frequency of the data. The input parameters are passed to the pipeline through a rather simple JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) configuration file, which is the case with all the input parameters of this AutoML pipeline.

Algorithm 1 FindFrequency

```

input
1:  $x$  ▷ Input TS data
2:  $sampling\_rate$  ▷ Sampling rate, default is 1
output
3:  $period$  ▷ Dominant frequency's period

4:  $n \leftarrow \text{length of } x$ 
5:  $x\_detrended \leftarrow \text{detrend}(x)$ 
6:  $fft\_result \leftarrow \text{FFT}(x\_detrended)$ 
7:  $spec \leftarrow |fft\_result|$ 
8:  $freq \leftarrow \text{FFT frequencies with rate } sampling\_rate$ 
9:  $peaks \leftarrow \text{find\_peaks}(spec, \text{height} = 10)$ 
10: if length of  $peaks > 0$  then
11:    $dominant\_freq \leftarrow$  ←
      $|freq[peaks[\text{argmax}(spec[peaks])]]|$ 
12:    $period \leftarrow \text{round}(1/dominant\_freq)$ 
13:   if isinf( $period$ ) then
14:      $nextmax \leftarrow peaks[0] + \text{argmax}(spec[peaks[0] +$ 
      $1 : \text{length of } freq])$ 
15:     if nextmax < length of  $freq$  then
16:        $period \leftarrow \text{round}(1/|freq[nextmax]|)$ 
17:     else
18:        $period \leftarrow 1$ 
19:     end if
20:   end if
21: else
22:    $period \leftarrow 1$ 
23: end if
24: return  $period$ 

```

B. Zero-shot Inference

Our AutoML system utilizes and extends TimeGPT, the first foundation model for TS. This GenAI model can be leveraged in data-driven decision-making processes, empower confident navigation through uncertainties, and mark a new era by democratizing access to cutting-edge predictions. The platform's simplicity and swiftness are exemplified in its ability to handle single or multiple series, requiring no training – a revolutionary characteristic. Trained on an extensive dataset of over 100 billion of hourly, daily, weekly, and monthly data points encompassing IoT and energy data, among others, TimeGPT disrupts the landscape of time-series analysis. Our proposed framework extends the functionality of the model to handle minute-level data points and enhances its flexibility for fine-tuning with proprietary data, facilitating informed strategic decisions tailored to specific domains.

The data are prepared for zero-shot inference in the previous stages as explained in Section III-A, and are passed to the prediction stage, along with the required metadata, such as frequency. The AutoML pipeline leverages TimeGPT-1 for zero-shot inference, meaning that no fine-tuning is performed

Fig. 1: Auto-TimeGPT pipeline.

on the data. The prediction results are now ready for the next stage, accuracy evaluation.

C. Domain Adaptation

The prediction results are evaluated in terms of accuracy, and if the evaluation stage is successful, then the model is ready to be used and served. The evaluation stage maintains accuracy thresholds in order to assess the accuracy performance of the model. These thresholds are empirically acquired through thorough experimentation. Cross-validation is used to perform systematic evaluation, employing a rolling-window scheme to meticulously evaluate the performance of the model across different time periods, thereby ensuring the reliability and stability of the model over time, while preventing model overfitting. In case the model does not pass the evaluation stage, then a fine-tune job is triggered, resulting in a model more adapted to the domain of the data, and prediction and evaluation stages repeat. Low Rank Adaptation (LoRA) is used for the fine-tuning job, using four as the rank for the dimensionality of the trainable matrices that are added to the original model weights, controlling the precision of the adjustments, and significantly reducing the number of trainable parameters from 210M to 1.9M. We use AdamW as the optimizer, commonly used with transformers, while excluding the bias term from weight decay.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Datasets

Server Room Data: Real-world server room data of temperature and humidity IoT measurements from a Raspberry Pi 4 device [14]. The dataset size is 555 one-minute based data points, resulting in 9 hours and 15 minutes total duration.

CDN Traffic Data: Real-world anonymized data from an operational multimedia streaming Content Delivery Network (CDN) [15] deployment in US over 5G infrastructures. The dataset size is 14,000 data points, consisting of bandwidth measurements, number of requests and edge cache hits. Each consecutive data point is separated by a one-minute interval, meaning that the dataset contains data for 9 days and 7 hours.

Infrastructure Resource Usage Data: This dataset is simulated in an on-premises cluster with the use of TANDEM edge platform manager [16]. It consists of four resource usage metrics, namely Memory and CPU Consumption, Received

and Transmitted Throughput. The dataset contains 11,520 data points. Each data point is the 1 minute average of the corresponding metric, totalling in 8 days of measurements.

5G Traffic Data: Generated synthetic data, based on real-world traffic patterns [17]. Dataset size is 19,887 data points, consisting of throughput in Mbps (Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) slice). Each consecutive data point is separated by a five-minute interval, approximating data for 2.4 months.

B. Accuracy of Zero-shot Inference

In this evaluation setting, Auto-TimeGPT was used without re-training its weights, with a forecasting horizon of 1 for minute-level data and 5 for five-minute level data. Our approach is compared against cutting-edge approaches based on reprogramming of LLMs, namely LLMTime [18] and Time-LLM [19], as well as battle-tested DL approaches, namely those models are: an RNN-based model, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), a transformer model, Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) and an MLP-based model, Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for TS Forecasting (N-HiTS).

The results are shown in Figure 2, where Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) was used as the accuracy metric. In the Infrastructure dataset, Auto-TimeGPT is comparable with the accuracy of LSTM, and TFT achieves the best accuracy in this experimentation setting. An out-of-domain inference is evaluated in the CDN Traffic dataset case, where the domain-agnostic Auto-TimeGPT was employed. In this context, LSTM achieves the best accuracy and Auto-TimeGPT has only 1.7 times lower accuracy, while performing similarly to Time-LLM. In the 5G Traffic dataset, LLMTime has 1.1 times higher accuracy than Auto-TimeGPT, while N-HiTS achieves the best accuracy, with TFT performing similarly.

While it is true that accuracy is amongst the most presented metrics when it comes to TSF performance, it is worth noting that Auto-TimeGPT, a general purpose approach, was used without any fine-tuning nor training on the datasets of this evaluation, while the dataset-specific benchmark models were trained and optimized on each specific dataset from scratch. Moreover, the time and effort each experiment requires, showcases the value of our approach. In the 5G Traffic dataset, with a size of around 20,000 points, the average time for performing the experiment was one hour per ML model, while

Fig. 2: Accuracy comparison of ML models on different datasets measured with MAPE. Time-LLM, LLMTime and Auto-TimeGPT perform zero-shot inference. The rest of the models are trained and optimized on each data set separately.

our approach required less than a minute, yielding a 60 times speedup of the end-to-end (E2E) process, i.e. from the moment that the experienced ML engineer received the dataset, until the moment that the accuracy metrics were generated.

C. Fine-tuning

The evaluation in Section IV-B was performed with no fine-tuning, i.e. zero-shot inference. In order to adapt to a particular domain, fine-tuning capabilities are also supported, especially useful for data from new domains. In this evaluation setting, we focus on the CDN Traffic dataset, and start fine-tuning the model with steps ranging from 0 to 500. As shown in Figure 3, the accuracy is ~ 1.2 times better after 100 steps when compared to no fine-tuning. Note that after 100 steps, the accuracy improvements are negligible, justifying 500 being the last fine-tune step number to be evaluated.

D. Anomaly Detection

We perform IoT anomaly detection on the Server Room dataset, focusing on abnormal humidity and temperature values. The edge platform EdgeX Foundry and the IoT messaging protocol Eclipse Mosquitto (MQTT) are used for device identification and overall orchestration of this real-world IoT use case. For comparison, we implemented anomaly detection based on Prophet [20] algorithm developed by Meta. Furthermore, we employ a variable called `importance`, associated with every anomaly marked by the algorithm, which we define in Equation 1, representing the relative error of the actual

Fig. 3: Auto-TimeGPT accuracy performance with fine-tuning on the CDN Traffic data set measured by MAPE.

value, i.e. y_{actual} , and the predicted value, namely \hat{y} . The magnitude of this variable gives a sense of how large the error is relative to the actual value. A cut-off threshold is used to drop minor anomalies from the results, in order to obtain meaningful insights. The results, presented in Figure 4, showcase the different abilities of the two solutions, namely Prophet captures more effectively upper anomalies, while Auto-TimeGPT balances between lower and upper anomalies, although unable to detect some upper anomalies that were identified by Prophet. Humidity data has been intentionally concealed for visualization purposes. The performance with humidity anomaly detection was similar to the performance showcased with the temperature data.

$$importance = \frac{y_{actual} - \hat{y}}{y_{actual}} \quad (1)$$

V. CURRENT LIMITATIONS

The introduction of an AutoML framework that uses a foundation model in TS that can be used cross-domain uncovers fascinating insights, aiming at helping researchers and applied scientists. However, it also shows the limitations of the current stage of this work. Although LoRA is used for the domain adaptation, which is useful in resource-constrained environment scenarios (e.g. edge deployment), the framework is not yet suitable for Edge AI applications, since in the initial stage the focus was primarily on performance and generalization capabilities. Our approach could provide a Nano architecture, targeting edge devices and processing the data as close as possible to their sources. For example, the IoT use case presented in Section IV-D could benefit from such a Nano architecture, deploy the framework at the far edge, and perform

Fig. 4: Anomaly detection. Anomalies are marked red, predicted values range green and actual measurements black.

on-device data-analytics, formulating an Edge AI application Zero-shot inference requires no fine-tuning but may not achieve SoTA performance. However, the performance is comparable to cutting-edge DL techniques, which require training per each different dataset; a remarkable achievement considering the general purpose capability and early stage of this work.

Long horizon TS forecasting may result in the performance degradation of our approach. Despite the fact that we are working on improving this aspect of our work, it is worth mentioning some of the reasons behind this current limitation. Long horizon TS forecasting presents intricate challenges arising from the cumulative effects of prediction errors, dynamic changes in trends, and the evolving nature of patterns over extended forecasting periods. As the forecasting horizon lengthens, even minor inaccuracies in early predictions can accumulate, leading to substantial deviations from actual outcomes. Additionally, capturing changing trends and patterns becomes increasingly complex, requiring models to adapt to evolving conditions. Furthermore, the availability and quality of historical data, a critical foundation for accurate forecasting, may diminish over time, introducing noise and incompleteness that further complicates the forecasting process.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this work, we introduced a novel GenAI solution for TS analysis, particularly useful for Edge-Cloud orchestration frameworks, such as the CODECO management framework. Our approach democratizes AI analytics and predictive insights towards next generation, *AI-native* networks and communications domains, by leveraging the revolutionary zero-shot inference capabilities of TimeGPT-1. We conducted an extensive evaluation of the proposed framework against cutting-edge approaches based on LLMs and DL models using multiple real-world and synthetic datasets, focusing on accuracy performance, fine-tuning and anomaly detection. The results showcase an AutoML approach that comes close to the accuracy of SoTA models, while generalizing to new domains and effectively detecting anomalies. Finally, we discussed the current limitations of Auto-TimeGPT.

As future work, we plan to enrich Auto-TimeGPT with additional frequency capabilities and domains, and incorporate TinyML approaches, suitable for Edge AI.

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